

Número	Título	Autor(es)	Evento/Periódico	Ano	Abstract	Keywords
EP1	The potential of using the blended learning format in social universities in St. Petersburg	IGNATJEVA, Olga; PLATONOVA, Iuliia; PLETNEV, Alexander	International Conferences Digital Transformation and Innovation Management	2024	Studying the implementation of the blended learning format in higher education is currently an interesting and relevant topic. This article contains a study of the development potential of blended learning within a social university. The research question is determined, on the one hand, by the popularity and rapid spread of the distant learning component, and on the other hand, by its obvious limitations. The study was conducted using a survey method. The obtained data were processed using factor and regression analysis with the aid of the R programming language. Regression analysis made it possible to identify latent learning factors that affect the effectiveness of the blended learning format. The study revealed that distant learning does not allow one to fully develop communication skills and provide students with tacit knowledge. The authors of the article discovered and substantiated the need to use classical learning to transfer tacit knowledge, soft skills. It was also revealed that the Socratic method, which has proven itself in the field of teaching the humanities, cannot be applied in an online format. Based on the results of the study, recommendations were made for the development of the blended learning format in social universities.	Blended learning, Education, Communication skills, Helping professions, Tacit knowledge
EP2	Does intrinsic motivation mediate perceived artificial intelligence (AI) learning and computational thinking of students during the COVID-19 pandemic?	MARTÍN-NÚÑEZ, José Luis; AR, Anil Yasin; FERNÁNDEZ, Rodrigo Pérez; ABBAS, Asad; RADOVANOVIC, Danica	Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence	2023	The concept of Artificial Intelligence (AI), born as the possibility of simulating the human brain's learning capabilities, quickly evolves into one of the educational technology concepts that provide tools for students to better themselves in a plethora of areas. Unlike the previous educational technology iterations, which are limited to instrumental use for providing platforms to build learning applications, AI has proposed a unique education laboratory by enabling students to explore an instrument that functions as a dynamic system of computational concepts. However, the extent of the implications of AI adaptation in modern education is yet to be explored. Motivated to fill the literature gap and to consider the emerging significance of AI in education, this paper aims to analyze the possible intertwined relationship between students' intrinsic motivation for learning Artificial Intelligence during the COVID-19 pandemic; the relationship between students' computational thinking and understanding of AI concepts; and the underlying dynamic relation, if existing, between AI and computational thinking building efforts. To investigate the mentioned relationships, the present empirical study employs mediation analysis based upon collected 137 survey data from Universidad Politécnica de Madrid students in the Institute for Educational Science and the School of Naval Architecture and Marine Engineering during the first quarter of 2022. Findings show that intrinsic motivation mediates the relationship between perceived Artificial Intelligence learning and computational thinking. Also, the research indicates that intrinsic motivation has a significant relationship with computational thinking and perceived Artificial Intelligence learning.	Artificial intelligence, Computational thinking, COVID-19, Educational innovation, E-learning, Higher education, SDG 4, Soft skills
EP3	Teaching soft skills including online: a review and framework	ROGERS, Justine	Legal Education Review	2020	With Artificial Intelligence steadily advancing, emblematic of change broadly, many argue that soft skills will be the central determinants of a lawyer's success. Soft skills comprise a 'combination of competencies that contribute to how people know and manage themselves as well as their relationships with others'. However, there is real need for more scholarship on how to teach them at law school. Meanwhile, and accelerated by COVID-19, universities are changing their models in favour of online or blended learning. But again, there is very little research on what an online context can do to support soft skills learning. Indeed, online learning is associated with learner isolation, frustration, disengagement, all of which are at odds with socio-emotional skills development. This article provides a critical analysis of the meanings and importance of soft skills, and the structural factors against their prominence in legal education. It also reviews teaching practices across the tertiary sector, to provide frameworks and a set of strategies for teaching them to law students, with a focus on the digital format.	Soft skills, Digital learning, Interpersonal skills, Online learning, Legal education, Graduate capabilities

EP4	Generative AI in higher education: educators' perspectives on academic learning and integrity	VRAGÅRD, John; BRORSSON, Freddie; AGHAEE, Naghmeh	Proceedings of the 23rd European Conference on e-Learning, ECEL 2024	2024 Generative Artificial Intelligence (Gen AI), exemplified by models such as ChatGPT, has rapidly advanced, becoming a significant force in various sectors, including higher education. ChatGPT, a leading application of Gen AI, utilizes large language models (LLMs) to generate human-like text, providing capabilities that range from answering complex questions to facilitating software development. As these tools become increasingly integrated into academic environments, their impact on teaching and learning processes has become more under focus. However, there are not many studies focusing on the impact of such systems on students' performance and the use of such systems. This study therefore examines the impact of GPT tools on higher education, aiming to address the following research questions: How does the use of GPTs influence the teaching and learning process in higher education? What are the perceived impacts of GPTs on educational practices from university educators' perspective? The research employs a qualitative methodology, incorporating semi-structured interviews with educators from Swedish universities who have integrated GPT into their curricula. Data were transcribed and analysed using OpenAI's Whisper to extract key themes and insights. Data analysis was done through thematic analysis and categorizing the data using codes. The study uncovers a dual impact of GPT on education, while it offers substantial opportunities for enhancing productivity and personalized learning, it also raises significant concerns about academic integrity, over-reliance on AI, and the potential influences on students' soft skills. These findings contribute to the discourse on digital learning by highlighting the need for instructional and constructive integration of AI technologies such as GenAI, in educational settings. In addition, the rise and integration of GPT technology is irreversible, and we must adapt to it rather than return to old ways. Embracing AI's potential while addressing its challenges is essential for progress and innovation in this new era. The study emphasizes the importance of developing clear policies and guidelines to ensure that the benefits of GPT are realized without compromising the integrity of the educational process. As such, this research provides valuable insights for educators, policymakers, and scholars interested in the ethical and effective implementation of AI in higher education.	Generative AI, ChatGPT, Higher education, Academic integrity, Digital learning
EP5	The effect of emotional intelligence on higher education: a pilot study on the interplay between Artificial Intelligence, emotional intelligence, and e-Learning	ALENEZI, Abdullah	Multidisciplinary Journal for Education Social and Technological Sciences	2024 Integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) and E-learning platforms has become increasingly prevalent in the rapidly evolving landscape of higher Education. However, amidst this technological advancement, the role of Emotional Intelligence (EI) and its impact on the efficacy of AI-driven educational tools still needs to be explored. This pilot study seeks to elucidate the intricate relationship between Emotional Intelligence, Artificial Intelligence, and E-Learning in Higher Education. Drawing upon a multidisciplinary approach, this study investigates the correlation between students' Emotional Intelligence competencies and their engagement with AI-driven E-Learning platforms. The findings of this pilot study are expected to shed light on several critical aspects. Firstly, it aims to uncover how Emotional Intelligence influences students' receptivity to AI-infused E-Learning environments, potentially elucidating strategies for optimizing user experience and learning outcomes. Moreover, by exploring the reciprocal influence between Emotional Intelligence and AI algorithms, this research endeavors to contribute to the refinement of AI technologies, fostering greater personalization and adaptability in educational settings. Furthermore, this study endeavors to address the ethical implications inherent in the intersection of Emotional Intelligence, Artificial Intelligence, and E-Learning. By elucidating the potential risks and benefits associated with integrating these technologies, it seeks to inform policymakers, educators, and AI developers alike, facilitating the responsible deployment of AI-driven educational tools. Therefore, its innovative methodology and comprehensive approach aspire to pave the way for future research endeavors, ultimately enriching the educational landscape with insights prioritizing technological advancement and human well-being.	E-learning, Artificial intelligence, Emotional intelligence, Ethical implications, Engagement and personalization

EP6	Artificial Intelligence to improve learning outcomes through online collaborative activities	NALLI, Giacomo; AMENDOLA, Daniela; SMITH, Serengui	Proceedings of the 21st European Conference on e-Learning - ECEL 2022	2022	A key strategic objective of the University courses is the promotion and development of new and innovative teaching activities, also through the e-learning environment, with the aim of providing students with direct involvement in the learning process. Collaborative activities represent important and effective teaching methodologies that allow the improvements of learning outcomes through active learning. Furthermore, they can allow the development of soft skills because they enable learners to work together and practice critical reflection and conflict negotiation. Recently, online learning environments are being used to design and deliver assignments based on student work groups. Indeed, the development of digital technologies allows the organization of these online activities in a flexible way for both students and teachers. The goal of this work is to develop successful collaborative activities for undergraduate students to ensure the improvement of knowledge and soft skills on a specific topic. One of the fundamental factors that influence the success of collaborative learning is the students' group formation, which consists in the realization of heterogeneous groups in terms of cognitive resources, characteristics, and behaviors, composed by four or five students. However, the correct implementation of groups requires careful profiling of each student's behavior which can be difficult for the teacher to detect. In this work an intelligent software, developed using Artificial Intelligence algorithms, was used to assist the teacher in the realization of heterogeneous groups of students. It is composed of a Machine Learning model, consisting in clustering techniques applied to Moodle learning analytics performed to return clusters that identifies different students' profiles, and a specific algorithm that automatically organizes the groups, ensuring the heterogeneity including at least one student from each cluster. At the end of the execution the software returns the list of the heterogeneous groups to the teacher. The software was applied to assignments that required working group within a specific online course for university students, using a Moodle e-learning platform. The quantitative analysis demonstrated the effectiveness of the numerical method for group composition proposed in this work to ensure successful collaborative activities, confirmed also by the perceptions of the students on the course.	Collaborative activities, Machine learning, Moodle, E-learning
EP7	Design a robot as a double with micro-expression to participate in a virtual situational learning environment and its effect on students' learning performance	AI HAKIM, Vando Gusti; YANG, Su-Hang; WANG, Jen-Hang; LI, Yi-Jing; CHEN, Yi-Hsin; CHEN, Gwo-Dong	Proceedings of the 30th International Conference on Computers in Education	2022	One way to encourage students to keep on practicing and studying learning materials is to let them be aware of how they will perform if they are placed in the situational evaluation. Thus, there should be a mechanism to act as a double that can be trained and revised by students so they can watch, monitor, and learn their own performances. Besides, emotional intelligence has gained a lot of attention due to its potential in maintaining situational interactions. Such a skill can detect the micro-expression to grasp the true feelings and hence students can take the appropriate responses. Therefore, this study proposes a learning approach, where students can collaboratively design the robot as their double with micro-expression to participate in situational evaluation tests. To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed approach, a quasi-experiment was conducted with 90 undergraduate students who enrolled in a Hospitality Japanese course in Taiwan. Three classes were assigned randomly with different learning approaches. The experiment results indicated that the groups with a robot as a double showed significant positive effects in terms of learning motivation and anxiety. Furthermore, a group of students using a double robot with micro-expression exhibited better learning achievement, but their anxiety was also increased. Finally, the limitations of the study and some suggestions for improvement of this proposed approach are provided.	Robots for learning, Virtual situational learning environment, Double, Emotional intelligence, Micro-expression, Human-robot interaction, AI and robots in education, Situated learning, Collaborative learning, Scaffolding tool
EP8	Use of Natural Language Processing (NLP) tools to assess digital literacy skills	RODRIGUEZ-RUIZ, Jorge; ALVAREZ-DELGADO, Alvaro; CARATOZZOLO, Patricia	2021 Machine Learning-Driven Digital Technologies for Educational Innovation Workshop	2021	The framework for Education 4.0 highlights the need for new assessment models of digital competencies to be incorporated into the curricula of Higher Education Institutions. Additionally, including new artificial intelligence tools (AI) can significantly help assess student skills development more flexibly and effectively. This study versatily implemented natural language processing (NLP) tools to strengthen the active learning approach to developing adequate educational solutions. The NLP tools proved ideal for evaluating soft skills in engineering. The study sample comprised 286 students enrolled in sustainability and energy efficiency subjects during six consecutive semesters from 2019 to 2021. The study's mixed methodology used a four-group Solomon-type design with two types of validated instruments used as pre-Tests and post-Tests: a) qualitative (surveys, questionnaires, interviews, and rubrics) and b) quantitative (tools for statistical data management). The study results confirmed that NLP tools are helpful to reduce teachers' training biases in the evaluations of students' digital literacy skills. In addition, the results showed that NLP tools can complement the evidence that instructors share with students in review and feedback sessions and improve their perception of the validity and reliability of the assessment instruments.	Digital literacy, Educational innovation, Higher education, Skills assessment, NLTK with Python

EP9	Neural Deep Learning models for Learning Analytics in a digital humanities laboratory	CEBRAL-LOUREDA, Manuel; TORRES-HUITZIL, César	2021 Machine Learning-Driven Digital Technologies for Educational Innovation Workshop	2021	Given the significance that technology-enhanced learning (TEL) receives in learning analytics, this study presents a neural deep learning architecture aimed to enhance a smart environment of a digital humanities laboratory. Presented a humanistic subject/controversy, the students interacted by producing multi-modal data (text, images, sound, movement) captured and processed with programmed devices. The smart environment induces emotional states during students' interactions and tasks in various scenarios, capturing images and facial expressions to classify student emotions. This study set up a preliminary experiment, testing the learning analytics model to show how it works and what outputs could be obtained. Leveraging the benefits of non-contact sensor technology, affective computing, and artificial intelligence, we collected biometric and neurocognitive data to establish correlations in the learning production of students studying humanistic and artistic topics. Despite the extended opinion expressed in the literature that the humanities do not have solid references on which to base learning analytics, this study shows that much quantitative data is available in such resources.	Digital humanities, Neural deep learning, Learning analytics, Student-centered, Sentiment analysis, Educational innovation, Higher education
EP10	Enhancing learner affective engagement: The impact of instructor emotional expressions and vocal charisma in asynchronous video-based online learning	SUEN, Hung-Yue; HUNG, Kuo-En	Education and Information Technologies	2025	In the rapidly evolving landscape of higher education and adult learning, asynchronous video-based online learning has not only become the new norm but has also emerged as the cornerstone of instructional delivery for Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs). Despite its widespread adoption, this learning mode confronts a critical challenge: the inherent lack of social presence, posing a significant risk of diminishing learner affective engagement and, consequently, jeopardizing the efficacy of learning outcomes. Addressing this pressing issue, our study conducted a comprehensive analysis of 240 instructional videos from 240 distinct instructors on a MOOC platform, supplemented by 845 post-course learner feedback surveys from a diverse cohort of college students and adult learners. Using deep learning and statistical analysis, the research revealed that the on-screen presence of instructors does not inherently affect students' affective engagement. The study revealed that learners' affective engagement is affected by distinct combinations of the instructor's facial and paraverbal expressions, including happiness, surprise, and anger, which vary depending on whether the instructor is visible. The discovery that vocal attractiveness is a pivotal element in enhancing learners' affective engagement with instructional videos marks a paradigm shift in our understanding of digital andragogy and heutagogy. This study propels academic discourse by illuminating the critical role of instructor non-verbal cues in establishing social presence and facilitating emotional contagion within asynchronous video-based online learning but also provides educators and content creators with empirically-backed techniques to revolutionize video instruction and amplify affective engagement.	Affective computing, E-learning, Facial expressions, Nonverbal communication, Paraverbal communication, Voice quality
EP11	Emotional intelligence and implicit interdisciplinary skills: key components for effective digital and AI-enhanced learning	MAKHACHASHVILI, Rusudan; SEMENIST, Ivan; KOPYTINA, Anastasia; BAKHTINA, Anna; BILYK, Kateryna	Proceedings of the 18th International Multi-Conference on Society, Cybernetics and Informatics (IMSCI 2024)	2024	The theoretical problems of holistic, multidimensional modeling and prognostication of reality and society development are informed by the dialectics of deterministic and fuzzy interaction of objects, signs of their reception and interpretation (in the field of individual and collective consciousness), embodiment, consolidation and retransmission of the results of interaction of these systems of features in an event horizon that is qualified as a 'singularity' – the state-of-the-art of technology development that facilitates multiple unpredictable outcomes. Transformative shifts in the knowledge economy of the XXI century, Industry 4.0 and Web 4.0 development and elaboration of networked society, emergency digitization of all social communicative spheres due to pandemic measures have imposed pressing revisions onto interdisciplinary and cross-sectorial job market demands of university level education, curriculum design and learning outcomes. Transgression of "real life" into a digital format necessitates the adaptation of the educational process to the new requirements of online being and the new labor market in particular. To meet their needs, higher education must keep pace with the times and predict the soft and hard skills required in the online dimension. The article dwells on criteria measuring students' academic success in the digital environment. To distinguish implicit and explicit components of emotional intelligence requests in digital education, an additional empirical diagnostics of students' interaction with AI-enhanced technologies and tools was conducted. Incremental skills for productive online education, as a property that can be acquired during learning (incremental implicit theory), and stable skills, constant and unchanging (stable implicit theory) were distinguished. The impact of emotional intelligence and implicit/explicit abilities on academic success is discussed.	Emotional intelligence, Artificial Intelligence, Interdisciplinarity, Digital education, Implicit skills, Explicit skills

EP12	Experiences on the creation of a multi-disciplinary course in a metaverse environment	KONTIO, Elina; RAVYSE, Werner; SAARENPA, Teppo; HAAVISTO, Timo; LUJIMULA, Mika	Proceedings of the 19th International CDIO Conference, hosted by NTNU, Trondheim, Norway	2023	<p>COVID-19 and climate change have both influenced the way we will organize higher education in the future. Turku University of Applied Sciences has developed its own metaverse technology to be used in higher education and industrial competence training. In this paper, we will report how this technology has been adapted to the requirements of higher education in medical sciences and health technology as part of the international Erasmus+ funded Artificial intelligence, innovation & society (AIIS) project which identifies a requirement for immersive multi-user learning. The AIIS project's main objective is to provide a course for medical students and health technology engineering students, where AI, innovation, and soft skills will play a key role, promoting the integration of the course into European universities' curricula. Combining metaverse technology with students from medical and engineering disciplines will allow us to simulate real-life problem-solving very closely while offering participants the unique possibility to deepen their professional understanding and multidisciplinary knowledge. The project's goals support CDIO's idea on providing integrated learning experiences (standard 7) and active learning (standard 8). This paper outlines our pedagogy considerations based on a sound theoretical framework and how we translated these considerations to suit the constraints and opportunities afforded by a metaverse environment that should be appropriate for both desktop and virtual reality headset users. Moreover, we examine content formatting, course pacing, assessment, and knowledge origin as the key elements of a typical learning landscape and how to adapt these for a metaverse setting. Additionally, to confirm the design choices for content and task presentation in a metaverse, this paper briefly gives the headline results of a large-scale pilot that was run at the time of this writing. Our paper contributes a comprehensive first draft pedagogy model for a metaverse collaborative learning environment, providing a practical contribution for educators venturing into metaverse-based teaching and a theoretical springboard for researchers to further enhance the body of knowledge concerning contemporary education technologies.</p>	Metaverse, Collaborative Learning, Virtual Learning Environment (VLE), Artificial Intelligence, CDIO standard 7, CDIO standard 8
EP13	Fostering digital literacy through active learning in engineering education	CARATTOZZOLO, Patricia; ALVAREZ-DELGADO, Alvaro; SIRKIS, Gabriela	2021 IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference (FIE)	2021	<p>This Research-to-Practice Full Paper discusses the use of the active learning approach to enhance the 21st century skills that are critical to developing new job opportunities for young engineers. The soft skills required in the Fourth Industrial Revolution make the traditional mode of logical-scientific thinking insufficient for the degree of innovation and disruption required in future jobs. In the field of higher engineering education, the situation was doubly challenging: Generation Z students' cognitive skills had to be improved in terms of digital literacy and cutting-edge technological tools had to be quickly incorporated. This work is a study on the effectiveness of the didactic approach of Active Learning in STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Art and Mathematics) and the innovative ways of empowering students to develop digital literacy skills, among them: photo-visual ability, reproduction ability, branching ability, real-time critical thinking ability and, the most important of this study, socio-emotional ability. The opportunities and challenges that the study addressed were related to accessibility, inclusion, and self-paced learning. The research was carried out with a mixed experimental methodology in a sample of 352 engineering students, who were evaluated with different types of instruments to know the level of acquisition of soft skills related to digital literacy. To evaluate these skills, different assessing instruments were used for pre-tests and post-tests, including: vocabulary level, lateral thinking ability, fluency and originality, as well as story-articulation skill tests and modified VALUE rubrics from the Association of American Colleges and Universities (AAC&U). The results obtained showed that the active learning approach promoted a better understanding of scientific concepts in engineering subjects, a greater ability to develop digital communication skills, and a greater awareness of creative thinking skill.</p>	Educational innovation, Higher education, Soft skills in engineering, Education 4.0, STEAM

EP14	Integration of AI into the Distance Learning Environment: enhancing soft skills	BORKOVSKA, Inna; KOLOSOVA, Hanna; KOZUBSKA, Iryna; ANTONENKO, Inna	Arab World English Journal (AWEJ)	2024 Soft skills have become increasingly essential for success in the modern world, especially in the labor market, where employers value employees' social and communication skills. Online education, which is an integral part of the educational process in Ukraine, is adjusting to the development of students' soft skills. Integrating artificial intelligence tools into English language learning is becoming a new direction in soft skills development. This approach opens up new teaching strategies that make learning more effective, engaging, and innovative. While learning English, students develop communication, creativity, and critical thinking skills, which contribute to their educational process and prepare the foundation for employment. The study aims to 1) evaluate the impact of artificial intelligence on the development of students' soft skills in online learning; 2) identify the most essential soft skills for their effective learning and future employment based on a student survey; 3) develop criteria for an online course using artificial intelligence and outline strategies for integrating the ChatGPT tool into distance learning English classes. To achieve the objectives of our study, we developed and processed a questionnaire, collected quantitative data, and analyzed and interpreted qualitative data; the study sample included 304 students. The questionnaire results showed a generally positive attitude of students towards using artificial intelligence in English for Specific Purposes courses. They opened up prospects for introducing an online course in the English for Specific Purposes program and further research, including an experiment with the introduction of this online course.	Artificial intelligence, Distance education, English for specific purposes, ChatGPT, Higher education, Smart technologies, Soft skills.
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